

Spouse Relocation and Work-Family Conflict as Determinants of Marital Satisfaction Among Young Married Couples in Ikenne Local Government Area of Ogun State, Nigeria

Thelma C. Nwaneri

Department Of Education, Babcock University, Ilisan-Remo, Nigeria

&

Ngozi Caroline Uwannah, PhD

Department of Education, Babcock University, Ilisan-Remo, Nigeria

uwannah@babcock.edu.ng [Tel:+2348062452415](tel:+2348062452415)

Abstract

The essence of marriage is to provide a foundation for emotional support, companionship, intimacy, and personal and family growth. Therefore, the study investigated spouse relocation and work-family conflict as determinants of marital satisfaction among young married couples in Ikenne Local Government Area of Ogun State, Nigeria. The study adopted a cross-sectional survey research design. The population of this study comprised legally married young couples of not more than 40 years of age and not more than 5 years of marriage by the end year 2024, living within the five towns that made up Ikenne Local Government Area of Ogun State with a sample size of 385 determined using stratified random sampling technique. An instrument titled Spouse Relocation, Work-family Conflict and Marital Satisfaction (SRWCMS) was employed to elicit data for the study. Simple table and percentage analysis (descriptive statistics) was adopted to describe and analyze the data gathered on the respondents' demographics and the research questions. Simple regression analysis was adopted to test hypotheses one and two while multiple regression analysis was employed to test hypothesis three, all at 0.005 significant level or error margin. Findings from the regression analysis revealed that spouse relocation has significant influence on marital satisfaction of the couples ($R = 0.318$; $R^2 = .101$; $R^2 \text{ Adj.} = .099$; $F_{(1,355)} = 8.416$; $p = .000$). Similarly, a significant impact of work-family conflict on marital satisfaction of the couples was found ($R = 0.490$; $R^2 = .240$; $R^2 \text{ Adj.} = .238$; $F_{(1,355)} = 112.316$; $p = .000$). Lastly, work-family conflict and spouse relocation were found to have joint significant impact on marital satisfaction among young married couples in Ikenne Local Government Area of Ogun State, Nigeria ($R = 0.554$; $R^2 = .307$; $R^2 \text{ Adj.} = .303$; $F_{(2, 354)} = 74.494$; $p = 000$). These variables (work-family conflict and spouse relocation) accounted for 30.7% of the variance in marital satisfaction of the couples. It is recommended that leaders of religious and educational institutions should periodically organize seminars and workshops for those couples to help their marriages grow and achieve desired satisfaction.

Received: 4 April 2025

Revised: 10 April 2025

Accepted: 17 April 2025

Copyright ♥ authors 2025

157

DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.15273077](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15273077)

Key words: Spouse Relocation, Work-Family Conflict, Marital Satisfaction, Young Married Couples

I. INTRODUCTION

In the preceding decades, marriage has drawn the attention of scholars, therapists, media, and other concerned individuals and groups. The goal of every marriage is to ensure that couples derive marital satisfaction or fulfilment in their relationship, and at such cases of marital crises, broken homes, spousal separation, and failed marriages are -aberration and must be prevented. However, in recent times, married couples could easily be seen complaining, quarrelling and even fighting loudly and publicly on issues bordering on discontent in their marriage relationships. This situation has left many individuals to wonder whether marital satisfaction is achievable and maintainable, proving a need for identifying ways of achieving marital success.

Marital satisfaction may be described as an individual's overall positive perception or assessment towards their marriage. It further indicates how content or fulfilled couples feel in their marital life. Many factors are often highlighted to be responsible for achieving marital satisfaction; although these factors vary from one person to another. Basic ingredients such love, peace, understanding and growth are common desire for couples to experience fulfilled marriage.

The challenges facing marital satisfaction appear to scare many unmarried persons to consider whether or not to get married. This situation might be responsible for decline in the rate of marriage initiation as many prospective husbands and wives are challenged and discouraged by what they see in some marriage relationships. In Africa, cases of failed marriages are not well-documented especially in Sub-Saharan Africa. However, research shows that marital crises are more common in western Africa than in the East (National Healthy Resource Centre, 2020). Historical analyses of the region point to the strength of familial bonds through lineage, as opposed to marital bonds, as the reason behind incidents failed marriages.

Moreover, the issue of poor reporting of failed marriage cases is prevalent in Nigeria. Consequently, according to Divorce.com (2023), Nigeria has the highest cases of failed marriages in Africa. The country followed by other African countries such as Egypt, Algeria, Tunisia, Sudan, Mauritius, Libya, South Africa, Ethiopia, Kenya, Zimbabwe, and Mozambique. This situation has been blamed on breakdown in trust and communication, making it difficult for couples to maintain a healthy and committed relationship (Omosola, 2024). Olagundoye and Odunjo-Saka (2022) report that one in three marriages break down in less than three years of the union. Chioma and Sulong (2022) also lamented about under reported but high cases of spousal separation in Nigeria. These suggest that a good number of Nigerian couples are facing issues bordering on marital satisfaction.

Marital satisfaction could be affected by several factors. For example, findings from Uwannah et al (2019) reveal that academic stress and workload have significant individual influences on marital satisfaction. Earlier, Sotude and Dindar (2015) demonstrate that couples' sexual performance and satisfaction of sexual relations are considered as part of the factors influencing marital satisfaction. Satisfaction of sexual relations in this case tends to be the preface of marital satisfaction. Satisfactory sexual relations have been highlighted as among the most important factors resulting to marital satisfaction and health.

Deriving marital satisfaction requires meeting the need for love and being loved; achieving socio-economic, psychological, and financial needs; changing generational status, gaining a place in the society, feeling safe and protected, cooperation, having confidence in the future, and maintaining a functional marriage and fulfilled marriage (Saravana et al, 2023). To attain these cited feats, married couples make certain decisions including having one of the spouses relocating or living differently from the other, here referred to as spouse relocation. Spouse relocation occurs when a husband or wife moves or migrates from his or her matrimonial home or dwelling place to settle in another area. The new place of settlement could be in the same geographical farther place, city or another country. The researcher observes that many spouses (especially young ones) in Nigeria relocate from their marital homes to various locations for several reasons such as career progression, economic prosperity (greener pasture), educational advancement, better healthcare services, security and safety of life, and escape conflicts for the benefit of their families.

The concept of spouse relocation appears to be a new area of research as there are no literatures on this. However, much attention is being given to relocation or migration to foreign countries otherwise referred to as “japa” syndrome in some studies (Okunade & Awosusi, 2023; Olumoyo & Abiri, 2023; Fasina, 2024). Japa in most cases used to be an agreement between couples for the benefit of their family. However, whether a spouse relocates within or outside the country of his or her matrimonial home, this situation impact on their family dynamics. The emotional toll on members of the family – spouses, children, parents, siblings, and extended family members can be immense. These members of the family are often faced with the challenge of adapting to changes in roles and responsibilities, especially when a primary breadwinner leaves. This can also lead to increased stress and strained relationships within the family unit and could also impact mental health significantly due to adjustment and adaptation challenges like loneliness, anxiety and depression (Fasina, 2024).

Further, research on marital satisfaction has led to identifying the effect of work-family relationship to the fulfilment of marital union (Ginanjari et al., 2020). The imbalance between family life and work can make couples experience excessive fatigue and stress. Where spouse cannot balance these roles, they will be vulnerable to stress due to role conflict (Widiningtyas, 2022). Some studies have proven that in aspects of family life, the demands of various roles can affect family satisfaction, life satisfaction, and marital satisfaction (Suswanto et al., 2022; Widiningtyas, 2022).

Work and family interfere with each other and can cause conflicts. Thus, work-family conflict (WFC) occurs when work interferes with family life, and it is often regarded as a kind of stressor which require much time and energy to satisfy the two domains (Wu & Wang, 2022). According to Oge et al (2018), when individuals experience stress in one domain, they will invest more resources in that domain to reduce stress. Couples, especially wives, who have dual career, work becomes their focus and attention is divided between the family (marriage) and the work (Layalin & Huda, 2023). Where these roles cannot balance, the wife will be vulnerable to stress due to role conflict (Widiningtyas, 2022). The work of Uwannah (2023) reveals that reduced work-family conflict is one of the factors that contribute to job commitment and satisfaction of working mothers in public universities in southwest, Nigeria.

Achieving marital satisfaction is crucial for family success, with many contributing factors. Examining the effect of spouse relocation and work-family conflict on marital satisfaction especially for young couples who are new in the marriage relationship is crucial in Ikenne municipal council where marital satisfaction issues are evident.

Conceptual Model

This model examines the graphic relationship of the independent variables with that of the dependent variable as shown below:

The above model demonstrates that H₁ (spouse relocation) was examined against marital satisfaction; H₂ (work-family) was investigated against marital satisfaction; while H₃ tested the joint relationship between the independent variable proxies against that of dependent variable.

Statement of the Problem

Marriage is one of the oldest institutions established for companionship, love and intimacy, and procreation, with the ultimate goal of achieving satisfaction. As the first step to family relationship, the experience of peace, joy, and happiness in a marriage all amounts to marital satisfaction. However, marriage have been confronted by a variety of challenges ranging from physical, socio-cultural, economic, and religious to legal issues truncating its fulfilment. These challenges have resulted to marital crises and frustrations leading to spouses' mental health conditions such as depression, anxiety, bipolar, and dementia.

Efforts to tackle the challenges faced by marriages have included frequent renewal of marital vows and commitments made by married couples on their anniversaries; marriage lecture presentations for both married and intending, seminars and workshops organized by educational, religious, and published researches made available by scholars to strengthen married and intending couples as well as the general public. Whereas these efforts are being carried out periodically, incidence of marital crises and dissatisfaction still persist.

Declining marital satisfaction will further affect immediate families' intimacy and connection, unity and progress, communication channels, finances, businesses, and ultimately, resulting to the ever-increasing family breakups. The general rippling effect of marital crisis includes worsened cases of failed marriages, marital apathy, increased cases of sexual immorality, infidelity, rape, increased single parenting, increased cases of "baby mamas" and "baby papas," problems associated with children upbringing, prostitution, substance abuse, and suicide. Hence, this study intends to contribute to ensuring marital satisfaction by examining the effect of spouse relocation and work-family conflict on the marital satisfaction among young married couples in Ikenne Local Government Area of Ogun State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The general objective of the study is to examine spouse relocation and work-family conflict as determinants of marital satisfaction among young married couples in Ikenne Local Government Area of Ogun State, Nigeria. However, the specific objectives of the study are to:

- i. Investigate the influence of spouse relocation on marital satisfaction of young married couples in Ikenne Local Government Area
- ii. Assess the influence of work-family conflict on marital satisfaction of young married couples in Ikenne Local Government Area
- iii. Determine the influence of spouse relocation and work-family conflict on marital satisfaction of young married couples in Ikenne Local Government Area

Research Hypotheses

H₀₁ There is no significant influence of spouse relocation on marital satisfaction of young married couples in Ikenne Local Government Area

Received: 4 April 2025

Revised: 10 April 2025

Accepted: 17 April 2025

Copyright ♥ authors 2025

- H₀₂ There is no significant impact of work-family conflict on marital satisfaction of young married couples in Ikenne Local Government Area
- H₀₃ Spouse relocation and work-family conflict will not have significant influence on marital satisfaction of young married couples in Ikenne Local Government Area

II. METHOD

The study adopted a cross-sectional survey research design. The population comprised legally married young couples living within the five towns that made up Ikenne Local Government Area of Ogun State namely Ikenne, Iperu, Ilisan, Ogere, and Irolu, made up of young couples not more than 40 years by the end year 2024. The sample size for the study was 385 obtained using stratified random sampling technique. The research instrument adopted for this study was a close-ended type of questionnaire titled “Spouse Relocation, Work-family Conflict and Marital Satisfaction (SRWCMS).” The researchers employed content and construct validity to assess the instrument’s validity while to ascertain the reliability of the research instrument, a pre-test of the questionnaire was conducted using ten (10) respondents outside the population. The instruments were found to be both reliable and valid.

Table 1: Summary Result of Reliability and Validity Tests

S/N	Variable	No of Questions	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)	KMO Validity	Cronbach's Alpha	Sig.
1	Spouse Relocation Variable	8	0.700	0.852	0.993	0.000
2	Work-Family Conflict	11	0.932	0.821	0.998	0.000

3	Marital Satisfaction	11	0.932	0.821	0.998	0.000
				0.83	0.99	0.000

Source: Researcher’s SPSS Computation Result, 2025

Both descriptive and inferential statistics were applied to analyze the data collected for the study. This enabled the researcher to examine the characteristics of the variables under study. Specifically, simple table and percentage analysis was adopted to describe and analyze the data gathered on the respondents’ demographic information. On the other hand, the Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) analysis was used to test hypotheses one and two while multiple regression analysis was adopted to test hypothesis three, all at 0.05 level of significant or error margin. These analytical tools are contained in the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23. The researchers complied with all laid down ethical rules and guidelines of Babcock University with respect its academic research under the supervision of Babcock University Health Research Ethics Committee (BUHREC).

III. RESULTS

Data presentations of this study are done based on the hypotheses earlier set. Three hundred and eighty-five (385) participants were estimated and participated in this study. All questionnaires were distributed but only three hundred and fifty-eight (358) were adequately filled and used in the analysis. Thus, 93% questionnaire retrieval success were ensured.

Socio-demographic profile of the study population
Table 2: Respondents' Socio-demographic profile

SN	Variable		N = 358	
			Freq.	%
1	Gender	Female	161	45.0
		Male	197	55.0
2	Age	21-25 years	35	9.8

Received: 4 April 2025

Revised: 10 April 2025

Accepted: 17 April 2025

Copyright ♥ authors 2025

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.15273077>

		26-30 years	84	23.5
		31-35 years	133	37.2
		36-40 years	78	21.8
		41-45 years	28	7.8
3	Years of marriage	0-5years	354	98.9
		6years above	4	1.1
4	Number of children	None	109	30.4
		1-3	201	56.1
		4 and above	16	4.5
5	Family Orientation	Monogamy	241	67.3
		Polygamy	83	23.2
6	Educational level	Secondary	19	5.3
		Advanced level	79	22.1
		Degree	238	66.5
7	Religion	Islam	98	27.4
		Christianity	223	62.3

The socio-demographic profiles of the study population based on the gender revealed that majority (55%) of the respondents were male. The respondents were within 21 to 53 years age range with a mean age of 34.7 ± 2.17 (SD). The majority 354 (98.9%) were married within 5 years, 241 (67.3%) were from monogamous home. For academic qualification of the respondents 238 (66.5%) were with a degree, and 223 (62.3%) were Christians.

Testing of Hypothesis

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant influence of spouse relocation on marital satisfaction of young married couples in Ikenne Local Government Area.

Received: 4 April 2025

Revised: 10 April 2025

Accepted: 17 April 2025

Copyright ♥ authors 2025

Table 6: Summary of Simple Regression Analysis for the influence of spouse relocation on marital satisfaction of young married couples

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	<i>T</i>	p-value
	<i>B</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>Beta</i>		
(Constant)	9.367	1.857		5.044	.000
Spouse Relocation	1.288	.204	.318	6.326	.000
Source of variation	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F-Ratio	P
Regression	654.428	1	654.428	40.013	0.00
Residual	5806.099	355	16.355		
Total	6460.527	356			

$R = 0.318$; $R^2 = .101$; R^2 (Adjusted) = .099; Stand error estimate = 4.044

The predictor variable (spouse relocation) contributed to the variance observed in marital satisfaction of young married couples. Table 6 revealed that spouse relocation has a *beta* = .318 and *t*-value of 6.326 significant at less than .05 alpha level. Therefore, spouse relocation is a potent factor to the prediction of marital satisfaction of young married couples. Furthermore, spouse relocation yielded a coefficient of multiple regression (*R*) of 0.318 and adjusted simple regression square of .101. This shows that 10.1% of the total variance in the marital satisfaction of young married couples is accounted for by spouse relocation. The table also indicated that the analysis of variance of the simple regression data produced an F-ratio value significant at .000 level ($F_{(1,355)} = 8.416$; $p = .000$). Therefore, the hypothesis that stated no significant influence of spouse relocation on marital satisfaction of young married couples was rejected.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant impact of work-family conflict on marital satisfaction of young married couples in Ikenne Local Government Area

Table 7: Summary of Simple Regression Analysis of influence of work-family conflict on marital satisfaction of young married couples

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	<i>t</i>	p-value
	<i>B</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>Beta</i>		

Received: 4 April 2025

Revised: 10 April 2025

Accepted: 17 April 2025

Copyright ♥ authors 2025

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15273077>

(Constant)	14.296	.666		21.474	.000
Work-family conflict	.348	.033	.490	10.598	.000
Source of variation	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	<i>F-Ratio</i>	<i>P</i>
Regression	1552.739	1	1552.739	112.316	0.00
Residual	4907.787	355	13.825		
Total	6460.527	356			
<i>R</i> = 0.490; <i>R</i> ² = .240; <i>R</i> ² (Adjusted) = .238; Stand error estimate = 3718					

The predictor variable (work-family conflict) contributed to the variance observed in marital satisfaction of young married couples. Table 7 revealed that work-family conflict has a beta value of .318 and *t*-value of 6.326 significant at less than .05 alpha level. Therefore, work-family conflict is a potent factor to the prediction of marital satisfaction of young married couples. Furthermore, work-family conflict yielded a coefficient of simple regression (*R*) of 0.490 and multiple regression square of .240. This shows that 24% of the total variance in the marital satisfaction of young married couples is accounted for by work-family conflict. The table also indicated that the analysis of variance of the simple regression data produced an F-ratio value significant at .000 level ($F_{(1,355)} = 112.316; p = .000$). Therefore, the hypothesis that stated no significant influence of work-family conflict on marital satisfaction of young married couples was rejected.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant impact of spouse relocation and work-family conflict on marital satisfaction of young married couples in Ikenne Local Government Area

Table 8: Model Summary of the Multiple Regression Analysis for the influence of spouse relocation and work-family conflict on marital satisfaction of young married couples

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	<i>t</i>	p-value
	<i>B</i>	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	5.190	1.683		3.084	.002
Work Family Conflict	.325	.032	.457	10.258	.000
Spouse Relocation	1.055	.180	.261	5.846	.000
Source of variation	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F-Ratio	P
Regression	1984.838	2	992.419	78.494	0.00
Residual	4475.689	354	12.643		
Total	6460.527	356			
<i>R</i> = 0.554; <i>R</i> ² = .307; <i>R</i> ² (Adjusted) = .303; Stand error estimate = 3.556					

The results in Table 8 indicated that with all the predictor variables (work family conflict and spouse relocation) in the regression model jointly predicted marital satisfaction of young married couples ($R = 0.554$; $R^2 = .307$; $R^2 Adj. = .303$; $F_{(2, 354)} = 74.494$; $p = 000$). This showed that the predictor variables (work family conflict and spouse relocation) accounted for 30.7% of the variance in marital satisfaction of young married couples. The null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant combined influence of work family conflict and spouse relocation on marital satisfaction of young married couples was rejected by this finding. This implies that there is a significant joint influence of work family conflict and spouse relocation on marital satisfaction of young married couples.

IV. Discussion

The outcome of the first hypothesis revealed a significant positive influence of spouse relocation on marital satisfaction of young married couples in Ikenne Local Government Area. Specifically, it was revealed that that 10.1% of the total variance observed in the marital satisfaction of young married couples is accounted for by spouse relocation. The reason for this finding could be attributed to the notion that when couples are not living together as a result of one of them looking for 'greener pasture' or vice visa can push the marriage to a cliff of dissatisfaction or frustration. This finding corroborates the work of Er & Gokcearslan (2023) whose finding reveals that long-term relocation due to military service assignments impact the marital satisfaction of soldiers in Turkey. Besides, the result of Pye and Simpson (2017) are in agreement with the finding of the present study. Pye and Simpson (2017) found that Family functioning and relationship of redeployed British soldiers affected the perceptions of their spouses and children on family happiness. Earlier, Hogan & Furst (2010) had found that military deployment and redeployment has negative influence on marriage longevity of soldiers who married while serving in the British army. The present study's finding further agrees with the work of Biedermann (2017)

Received: 4 April 2025

Revised: 10 April 2025

Accepted: 17 April 2025

Copyright ♥ authors 2025

167

who found that Australian military spouses experienced low marital satisfaction as a result of their spouses' overseas postings. However, the findings of Karney, Loughran and Pollard (2012) revealed a variation between marital satisfactions of civilian and military officers whose spouses separated from them as a result of work. Marital satisfaction was higher with the spouses of civilian officers when compared with their military counterparts. Similarly, Cag and Yildirim (2013) found that personal variables such as fulfilment of psychological needs influenced marital satisfaction. These findings are empirical evidences that spouse relocation significantly influences marital satisfaction of couples.

The outcome of the second hypothesis revealed a significant impact of work-family conflict on marital satisfaction of young married couples in Ikenne Local Government Area. Specifically, it was revealed that that 24% of the total variance in the marital satisfaction of young married couples is accounted for by work-family conflict. This shows that when the demands and pressures of work and family roles become incompatible, it makes it difficult to for young couples to fulfill both roles effectively, potentially leading to stress and strain, as well as affecting the marital life. This result is in support of the findings of Wulandari et al (2019) whose population were nurses who worked in hospital X in Purwokerto with a sample of 40 people (men = 6 people and 34 women). Their results of the data analysis showed a negative and significant contradiction between work-family conflict and marital satisfaction. This means that the higher the work-family conflict, the lower the marital satisfaction. These results can explain how roles in the family and workplace influence each other. Thus, work-family conflict influenced marital satisfaction of young married couples.

Similarly, Juniarily et al (2020) results indicated that there is a significant role of work-family conflict, and that work-family conflict have significant effect on marriage satisfaction on employees at Bank X. This result is consistent with the findings of Buyuksahin-Sunal et al (2022) who examined the relation between work family conflict and marital satisfaction via the mediating role of marital power on this relationship. The results indicate that marital power has an important role on the relation between family to work conflict and marital satisfaction. Also, Olagundoye and Odunjo-Saka (2022) reported that work-life balance (work-personal life enhancement) positively predicted marital satisfaction while work-life balance (personal life interference and work-personal life interference) negatively predicted marital satisfaction.

The third and the last hypothesis showed that the predictor variables (work family conflict and spouse relocation) accounted for 30.7% of the variance in the marital satisfaction of young married couples. This implies that there is a significant joint influence of work family conflict and spouse relocation on marital satisfaction of young married couples. This finding is consistent with previous studies conducted by Wu and Wang (2022) who explored the relationship between work-family conflict and its consequences on job, family, and marital satisfaction among stay-at-home wives of commuter couples by testing the moderating effect of commuters' family (parental, marital, and household) commitment. The results revealed that stay-at-home wives perceived more job dissatisfaction due to work-to-family conflicts and perceived more job, family, and marital

dissatisfaction caused by family-to-work conflicts. Additionally, Layalin and Huda (2023) results showed a significant positive effect of Work-Family Balance on Marital Satisfaction in the area. Sadiq et al (2024) results revealed that work-family conflict has significant relationship with anger and verbal aggression and thus, negatively affect marital satisfaction. It was equally observed that majority of women in the study were experiencing significant anger and verbal aggression.

V. Conclusion

Based on the results of this study, it can be concluded that spouse relocation and work-family are determinants of marital satisfaction among young married couples in Ikenne Local Government Area. This implies that the conflict spouses experience as a result of balancing work and family has a significant influence on their marital satisfaction. Similarly, the pressure encountered at the workplace affects the role of couples in the family to the extent that satisfaction in marriage decreases and vice versa. Conversely, the pressure faced by couples in relation to their role in the family can affect their performance in the workplace and their overall life satisfaction. Additionally, satisfaction in marriage was affected by spouse relocation among young married couples.

VI. Recommendations

This study has implication for family counseling. Counselors need to consider the relational communication pattern, couples' mutual vulnerability, and emotional attunement in order to improve the couples' marital quality and satisfaction hence it is recommended that leaders of marital education should organize workshops for those couples to help marriages in trouble, seek research validation of the effectiveness of their workshops. This validation should not be sought for the purpose of marketing or advertising, but for the purpose of determining whether the intensive marital education workshop is effective in achieving its goal in helping distressed marriages.

References

- Biedermann, N. (2017). Australian military spouses' experiences of overseas postings: a qualitative study. *Military Medicine*, 202, 53-62.
- Buyuksahin-Sunal, A., Ok, A. B., Kaynak-Malatyal, M. & Taluy, N. (2022). Relationship between work family conflict and marital satisfaction: Marital power as a mediator. *Nesne*, 10(24), 204-215.
- Cag, P. & Yildirim, I. (2013). Relational and personal variables predicting marital satisfaction. *Turkish J Psychol Couns Guid*, 4(39), 13-23.
- Chioma, R. U. & Sulong, R. M. (2022). Relationship between Compatibility, Leisure and Marital Satisfaction among Married Nigerians. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 12(10), 2652-2663.
- Er, F. & Gokcearslan, E. (2023). Assessment of Marital Satisfaction among Spouses of Soldiers: The Example of Turkey. *Military Medicine*, 188(9-10), e3160-e3166.

Received: 4 April 2025

Revised: 10 April 2025

Accepted: 17 April 2025

Copyright ♥ authors 2025

169

DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.15273077](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15273077)

- Fasina, M. (2024). The impact of “Japa Syndrome” on work and family relationships in Nigeria today. Accessed 1 August, 2024 from <https://businessday.ng/opinion/article/the-impact-of-japa-syndrome-on-work-and-family-relationships-in-nigeria-today/>
- Ginanjar, A.S., Primasari, I., Rahmadini, R. & Astuti, R.W. (2020). The Relationship between Work-Family Conflict and Work-Family Balance with Marital Satisfaction of Wife in Dual-Earner Families. *Jurnal Ilmiah Keluarga & Konseling*, 13(2), 112–124.
- Hogan, P. F. & Furst, S. R. (2010). Marriage and the military: evidence that those who serve marry earlier and divorce earlier. *Armed Forces Soc.*, 36(3), 420-38.
- Karney, B. R., Loughran, D. S., & Pollard, M. S. (2012). Comparing marital status and divorce status in civilian and military populations. *J Fam. Issues*, 33(12), 1572-94.
- Juniarly, A., Pratiwi, M., Purnamasari, A. & Nadila, T. F. (2020). Work-Family Conflict, Social Support And Marriage Satisfaction On Employees At Bank X. *Jurnal Psikologi*, 19(4), 343-356.
- Layalin, N.A. & Huda, E.A. (2023). The Impact of Work-Family Balance on Marital Satisfaction. *International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews*, 4(3), 1779-1782.
- National Healthy Resource Centre (2020). Marriage Trend in Africa: A Fact Sheet.
- Oge, E., Cetin, M. & Top, S. (2018). The effects of paternalistic leadership on workplace loneliness, work family conflict and work engagement among air traffic controllers in Turkey. *J. Air Transp. Manag.* 66, 25–35.
- Okunade, S. K. & Awosusi, O. E. (2023). The Japa syndrome and the migration of Nigerians to the United Kingdom: an empirical analysis. *Comparative Migration Studies*, 11(27), 1-18.
- Olagundoye, H. F. & Odunjo-Saka, K. A. (2022). Work-life balance and marital satisfaction among non-academic staff of Federal University, Oye-Ekiti. *Nigerian Journal of Behavioural Studies*, 1(1), 137-144.
- Olumoyo, A.E. & Abiri, O.C. (2023). “Japa” Syndrome: Causes, Effects and Solutions for Sustainable National Development. *International Journal of Development and Economic Sustainability*, 11(5), 87-95.
- Omosola, F. (2024). Nigeria among countries with highest divorce rate-Report. Assessed 2/10/2024 from <https://www.premiumtimesng.com/entertainment/naija-fashion/728808-nigeria-among-countries-with-highest-divorce-rate-report.html?tztc=1>
- Pye, R. & Simpson, L. (2017). Family functioning differences across the deployment cycle in British army families: the perceptions of wives and children. *Military Medicine*, 182(9 10), e1856–63.
- Saravana, K., Ramesh, B., Sachin, B.S. & Rajashekar, C. (2023). Marital Satisfaction among Newly Married Couples: A Post COVID Pandemic Study in India. *The International Journal of Indian Psychology* 11(3), July-September, 1-11.
- Sotude, M. & Dindar, R. (2015). Relationship between marital satisfaction, sexual satisfaction and social security in couples in Tehran. *Q Policing J Knowl Capital Police*, 8, 9-24.
- Staines, G. L. (1980). Spillover versus compensation: A review of the literature on the

- relationship between work and nonwork. *Human Relations*, 33(2), 111-129.
- Stepanek, S., & Paul, M. (2022, September 28). Umbrella summary: Work-family conflict. Quality Improvement Center for Workforce Development. <https://www.qicwd.org/umbrella/work-family-conflict>
- Suswanto, A., Noor, T. & Dewayani, E. (2022). Kepuasan perkawinan dan work family conflict pada guru perempuan Marital satisfaction and work-family conflict on female teacher. *Prosiding Seminar Nasional Fakultas Psikologi UMBY*, 65–74.
- Uwannah, N. C. (2023). Organizational Support, Work-Family Conflict and Job Tenure as Predictors of Job Commitment and Satisfaction among Working Mothers in Public Universities in Southwest, Nigeria. *European Journal of Human Resource Management Studies*, 7(1), 1-22.
- Uwannah, N. C., Aderanti, R. A., Starris-Onyema, P. N. & Mark, O. G. (2019). Academic Stress and Workload in Relation with Marital Satisfaction: A Study of Married Employed Students in Ogun State, Nigeria. *European Journal of Scientific Research* 153(4), 458-468.
- Widiningtyas, K. (2022). The dynamics of the dual role conflict of working mothers who undergo a dual earner family. *Psyche: Journal of Psychology, University of Muhammadiyah Lampung*, 4(2), 202–218.
- Wu, H.P. & Wang, Y.M. (2022). Women’s work–family conflict and its consequences in commuter marriages: The moderating role of spouses’ family commitment in a dyad analysis. *Frontier in Psychology*, 13(860717), 1-16.